

DESIGN FOR HAPPINESS & SUSTAINABLE SOCIETIES

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable Design, Design for Happiness and Well-being, and Sustainable Consumption present good opportunities, with strong potential, to change the current situation, improve the world foundations, and build more sustainable lifestyles and happier societies; although their relationship has not yet been studied widely in a systematic way, there are already many indicators which show that we can live happily and more sustainably, with much less material items and less consumption (Veenhoven 2004, Abdallah *et al.*, 2012). Through understanding the way in which design and the designer can contribute in a holistic way to the above mentioned, the Design for Happiness framework (DfH) (Escobar-Tello 2011) proposes an innovative design approach, process and tool-kit to design a 'sustainable material culture' (sustainable products, services or systems) capable of contributing to shaping and promoting society towards happiness and sustainable lifestyles underpinned by sustainable economic foundations.

BACKGROUND ISSUES, WORKSHOP GOAL, AND APPROACH

The overarching foundations of our current world structure have led to a 'material-centred culture' where the *systems of belief and values* pivot around externalities such as materialism and money. In the majority of countries around the world, particularly in western and developed countries, this 'culture' has been designed and marketed in unsustainable ways inviting users to buy and discard products more frequently (i.e., designing for obsolescence; fast-track consumption; cradle-to-grave design). Unfortunately, increasing evidence suggests that although economic growth has been increasing for the past 60 years or so, happiness and well-being, environmental and social capital, and sustainable lifestyles have been declining (Jackson and McBride 2005, Amna Silim 2012, Abdallah *et al.*, 2012).

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The results and analysis of the data gathered through the various workshops carried out so far, confirm that the DfH framework is successful in translating complex values (i.e., happiness, sustainable design, sustainable societies) into tangible design values, and hence bringing designers, as well as multidisciplinary agents, into an innovative design mind-set. More significantly, it is also a seed for building more sustainable societies where individuals lead sustainable lifestyles; essentially, for triggering societal systemic shifts and enabling a transition at a broad societal system level (Escobar-Tello 2014, expected publication).

Aim:

The aim of this workshop is therefore to offer its participants the opportunity to experience and apply the DfH framework. Throughout the workshop participants will have the opportunity to design products, services or systems (PSS) through the use of the DfH process and tool-kit, allowing them to embed the abovementioned complex values in their design proposals.

It will equip them with the skills to replicate such learning experience, and enable great potential for social innovation, driving sustainable change in business, organisations and society. Moreover, the workshop will add to the DfH research evidence portfolio, which so far has focused on developed economies (UK). This workshop seeks to provide further evidence of its value, application, and impact in cross-cultural environments, and highlight further implications for the design discipline.

Delivery:

The DfH is delivered through a co-design workshop setting providing an environment for its participants, ideally multidisciplinary agents, to design and create. Its process and tool-kit serve as a method to bring from a bottom up approach the characteristics and values of what is important and meaningful for people. Throughout its phases, the workshop participants will approach design from a different perspective. Collaborative design dialogues that support sustainable design innovation processes will result in systemic level changes (PSS) with high potential to contribute towards happiness and sustainable lifestyles as opposed to the restrictive product improvement level. Depending on the time available, the outcomes of the workshop will be at a stage where they can be tested in a ‘real world’ setting.

Followed by a presentation of the theory underpinning the DfH, the participants focus on the session’s design brief (a burning issue/problematic relevant to the context of delivery [i.e. Colombia]), immerse in a series of collaborative dialogues and idea generation stages, and give way to a series of conceptual design proposals. This workshop’s process follows five phases (Figure 1) and will be supported by the workshop’s facilitator and the framework’s tool-kit. Participants will work in small groups.

Intended number of attendees:

- Minimum 6
- Maximum 30

Length of the workshop:

- **Ideally** full day – 6 hours
- It can be accommodated to half-day too (3 hours)

Characteristics of the space/room needed to conduct the workshop:

- Open ‘studio’ space
- ‘Round’ tables that allow working in groups (4-5 people per group depending on number of attendees).
- Magnetic ‘white’ boards
- Computer or facilities to connect laptop.
- Screen projector; sound.
- Materials – A2 and A3 blank paper, markers.
- Website/blog

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Figure 1. Design for Happiness Workshop – Phases and Guiding Narrative (Escobar-Tello 2014)